

Teaching-Learning Mathematics through Experiments and Projects

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Abstract

Mathematics laboratory as a novel concept is an effective tool in the hands of a teacher to illustrate to the students that they can construct all mathematical knowledge with their own hands that enables them to develop abstract thinking capabilities and linking school knowledge to every day experience. The mathematics laboratory provides opportunities to teachers for demonstration, explanation and reinforcement of abstract mathematical ideas by using concrete objects, working and non-working models, different types of charts, graphs, pictures and posters. The mathematics laboratory also helps students in understanding, internalization, discovering and verifying the basic mathematical concepts through concrete objects and materials and therefore builds up interest and confidence in students learning the subject. In this article, the procedure to conduct some experiments and mathematical projects in Mathematics Laboratory is elaborated to help the teacher-trainees, teacher-trainer, teachers and students of Mathematics.

Keywords: *Mathematics, Mathematics Laboratory, Laboratory, Experimentation, Experiments, Projects*

Introduction:

A large section to student population considers mathematics to be a dull, boring and difficult subject. The reason of this is being taught in a mechanical manner where students are made to memorize formulae/algorithms and apply these formulae algorithms in solving problems, which results in leaving behind a large number of students who fear the subject. Fortunately, The National Curriculum Framework 2005 has elaborated on the insights of 'Joyful Learning without Burden' and introduced the concept of "Mathematics Laboratory" in schools up to secondary level.

Mathematics laboratory as a novel concept is an effective tool in the hands of a teacher to illustrate to the students that they can construct all mathematical knowledge with their own hands that enables them to develop abstract thinking capabilities and linking school knowledge to every day experience.

The mathematics laboratory provides opportunities to teachers for demonstration, explanation and

reinforcement of abstract mathematical ideas by using concrete objects, working and non-working models, different types of charts, graphs, pictures and posters. The mathematics laboratory also helps students in understanding, internalization, discovering and verifying the basic mathematical concepts through concrete objects and materials and therefore builds up interest and confidence in students learning the subject.

Mathematics laboratory should be a place for joyful learning furnished with economical and easily available material, concrete objects, geometrical instruments, models, charts, graphs, pictures etc. Teacher and students should collaborate in developing the models, charts, graphs, pictures & posters etc.

In this article, the procedure to conduct some experiments and mathematical projects in Mathematics Laboratory is elaborated to help the teacher-trainees, teacher-trainer, teachers and students of Mathematics.

Experiment-1

Topic: Arithmetic Progression (A.P.)

Learning Objective:

To verify that the given sequence is in Arithmetic Progression or not by paper cutting and pasting method.

Pre-requisite:

Understanding of the concept of an Arithmetic Progression.

Materials Required:

Glazed Papers, A Pair of Scissors, A Scale, Glue and Graph Papers.

Procedure:

(A)

Step 1: Take a sequence of numbers:

6, 9, 12, 15.....

Step 2: Cut a rectangular strip from a coloured glazed paper of width 1 cm and length 3 cm.

Step 3: Cut rectangular strips from glazed papers (of different colours) of width 1 cm and lengths 6, 9 cm, 12 cm, 15 cm

Step 4: Paste the coloured strips in ascending order (lengthwise) on a graph paper as shown

Figure 1.1

Step 5: Observe that the coloured strips form a ladder in which the difference between

the heights of the adjoining strips is constant (3 cm in this case).

∴ The given sequence forms an Arithmetic Progression.

(B)

Step 6: Take another sequence of numbers:

2, 5, 10, 11, 15,

Step 7: Cut a rectangular strip from a coloured glazed paper of width 1 cm and length 2 cm.

Step 8: Cut rectangular strips from glazed papers (of different colours) of width 1 cm and lengths 5 cm, 10 cm, 11 cm, 15 cm

Step 9: Paste the coloured strips in ascending order (length wise) on a graph paper as shown in Fig 1.2.

Figure 1.2

Step 10: Observe that the coloured strips form a ladder in which the difference between the heights of the adjoining strips is not constant.

∴ The given sequence is not an A.P.

Results (Learning Outcomes):

Common Difference	Sequence
Constant	A.P. Sequence
Not Constant	Not an A.P.

Experiment-2

Topic: Area of Similar Triangles.

Learning Objective:

To verify that the ratio of the areas of two similar triangles is equal to the square of the ratio of their corresponding sides by paper cutting and pasting method.

Pre-requisite:

- (i) Understanding of the concept of similar triangles.
- (ii) Understanding of the concept of congruent triangles.
- (iii) Construction of lines parallel to a given line.
- (iv) Divide a line-segment into a given number of equal parts.

Materials Required:

Procedure:

- Step 1:** Draw a triangle PQR on a drawing sheet.
Step 2: Divide line-segment PQ into 5 equal parts at the points A_1, A_2, A_3 and A_4 . Also divide line segment PR into 5 equal parts at the points B_1, B_2, B_3 and B_4 . (See Fig 2.1)
Step 3: Join the points A_1 and B_1, A_2 and B_2, A_3 and B_3, A_4 and B_4 .
Step 4: Observe that the line-segments A_1B_1, A_2B_2, A_3B_3 and A_4B_4 are parallel to the line-segment QR. (See Fig 2.1)
Step 5: Draw lines parallel to PR through the points A_1, A_2, A_3 and A_4 . Also draw lines parallel to PQ through the points B_1, B_2, B_3 and B_4 (See Fig 2.1)

Figure 2.1

- Step 6:** Observe that ΔPQR is divided into 25 small triangles. (See Fig 2.1)
Step 7: Colour these 25 small triangles with to alternative sketch colours. (See Fig 2.1)
Step 8: Draw another ΔLMN of sides $LM = \frac{PQ}{5} \times 7$ units, $MN = \frac{QR}{5} \times 7$ units and $NL = \frac{RP}{5} \times 7$ units similar to ΔPQR (See Fig 2.2)
Step 9: Divide line-segment LM into 7 equal parts at the points C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5 and C_6 . Also divide line segment LN into 7 equal parts at the points D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4, D_5 and D_6 (See Fig 2.2)
Step 10: Join the points C_1 and D_1, C_2 and D_2, C_3 and D_3, C_4 and D_4, C_5 and D_5, C_6 and D_6 .

Figure 2.2

- Step 11:** Observe that the line-segments $C_1D_1, C_2D_2, C_3D_3, C_4D_4, C_5D_5, C_6D_6$ are parallel to the line-segment MN. (See Fig 2.2)
Step 12: Draw lines parallel to LN through the points C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5 and C_6 . Also draw lines parallel to LM through the points D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4, D_5 and D_6 (See Fig 2.2)

- Step 13:** Observe that $\triangle LMN$ is divided into 49 small triangles. (See Fig 2.2)
- Step 14:** Colour these 49 small triangles with two alternative sketch colours. (See Fig 2.2)
- Step 15:** Make a replica of $\triangle PA_1B_1$, using coloured glazed paper and place it one by one on the rest of small triangles in Fig 2.1 and Fig 2.2.
- Step 16:** Observe that $\triangle PA_1B_1$ completely covers all the small triangles one by one simultaneously.
 \therefore All small triangles are congruent to each other and are of equal area.
- Step 17:** Each small triangle of $\triangle PQR$ is congruent to each small triangle of $\triangle LMN$ and these small triangles have equal area.

$$\begin{aligned}\therefore \frac{\text{Area of } \triangle PQR}{\text{Area of } \triangle LMN} &= \frac{\text{Sum of Area of 25 Small Congruent Triangles}}{\text{Sum of Area of 49 Small Congruent Triangles}} \\ &= \frac{25 \times 1}{49 \times 1} \\ &= \frac{25}{49} \text{ square units}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Also, } \frac{\text{Square of Base of } \triangle PQR}{\text{Square of Base of } \triangle LMN} &= \frac{(QR)^2}{\left(\frac{QR}{5} \times 7\right)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{5}{7}\right)^2 \\ &= \frac{25}{49} \text{ square units.}\end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \frac{\text{Area of } \triangle PQR}{\text{Area of } \triangle LMN} = \frac{(QR)^2}{(MN)^2} \text{ square units.}$$

Results (Learning Outcomes):

It is verified that the ratio of the areas of two similar triangles is equal to the square of the ratio of their corresponding sides.

Experiment-3

Topic: Making a Clinometer (Trigonometric Protractor).

Learning Objective:

To make a mathematical instrument clinometer and to use it to measure angle of elevation or depression, height of an object and distance between two objects.

Pre-requisite:

- (i) Knowledge about clinometers.
- (ii) Understanding of concept of trigonometric ratios and their values.
- (iii) Understanding of the concept of angle of elevation and depression.

Materials Required:

A Small Hollow Pipe (Viewing Tube), A Cardboard, A Pair of Scissors, Paint Box, Nails, Thread, Small Weight, Coloured Pens, Geometry Bob and Fevicol.

Procedure:

Step 1: Cut a semi-circular protractor from the cardboard and paint it. (See Fig 3.1)

- Step 2:** Make degrees with 0° at the lowest and 1° to 90° proceeding both clockwise and anticlockwise. (See Fig 3.1)
- Step 3:** Fix a hollow pipe along the diameter of the protractor. (See Fig 3.1)
- Step 4:** Fix a small nail at the centre of the semi-circular protractor. (See Fig 3.1)
- Step 5:** Using thread suspend a weight from the small nail. (Be careful that the length of thread must be greater than the radius of the semi-circular protractor) (See Fig 3.1)

Figure 3.1

Results (Learning Outcomes):

Clinometer is ready.

Experiment-4

Topic: Concentric Circles.

Learning Objective:

To prove that in two concentric circles, the chord of the larger circle, which touches the smaller circle, is bisected at the point of contact by paper cutting and pasting method.

Pre-requisite:

- (i) Understanding of the concept of concentric circles.
- (ii) Drawing a chord of the larger circle, which touches the concentric smaller circle.

Materials Required:

Drawing Sheets, Coloured Glazed Papers, Geometry Box, Glue, A Pair of Scissors and Sketch Pens.

Procedure:

- Step 1:** Draw two concentric circles say C_1 and C_2 with centre O on a drawing sheet. (See Fig 4.1)

Figure 4.1

- Step 2:** Draw a chord say AB of the larger circle C_2 which touches the smaller circle C_1 at P. (See Fig 4.1)
- Step 3:** Join the points O and P, O and A, O and B. (See Fig 4.1)
- Step 4:** Observe that two triangles OAP and OBP are formed.
- Step 5:** Colour the triangle OAP with red sketch pen and triangle OBP with blue sketch pen. (See Fig 4.1)
- Step 6:** Using coloured glazed paper make a replica of ΔOAP .
- Step 7:** Place the replica of ΔOAP at ΔOBP . (See Fig 4.2)

Figure 4.2

- Step 8:** Observe that the ΔOAP completely covers the ΔOBP and the points A and B coincide. (See Fig 4.2)

$$\therefore AP = BP$$

Results (Learning Outcomes):

It is verified that in two concentric circles, the chord of the larger circle, which touches the smaller circle, is bisected at the point of contact.

Experiment-5

Topic: Volume of a right Circular Cylinder.

Learning Objective:

To obtain the formula for volume of a right circular cylinder.

Pre-requisite:

- (i) Understanding of the concept of a right circular cylinder.
- (ii) Understanding of the concept of volume of solids.
- (iii) Understanding of formula for volume of Cuboid.
- (iv) Understanding of the concept of circumference of a circle and its formula.

Materials Required:

Solid Right Circular Cylinder Made of Plastic Clay, A Cutter, A Thermocol Sheet, A Scale and Paint Box.

Procedure:

Step 1: Take the given cylinder and mark its height h units and radius r units. (See Fig 5.1)

Figure 5.1

Step 2: Cut the cylinder vertically into 8 equal sectorial parts as shown in the figure 5.2.

Step 3: Paint 4 parts with green colour and 4 part with yellow colour.

Figure 5.2

Step 4: Further, cut each of the 8 sectorial parts vertically into two equal parts. (See Fig 5.3)

Figure 5.3

Step 5: Place two small parts at the two ends and rest 7 equal parts (yellow and green) alternatively on a thermocol sheet. (See Fig 5.4)

Figure 5.4

Step 6: Observe that the solid formed in such a way is a Cuboid with

$$\begin{aligned} \text{length} &= \frac{1}{2} \times \text{circumference of the circle} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \times 2\pi r = \pi r \text{ units} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{breadth} &= \text{radius of the Cylinder} \\ &= r \text{ units} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{height} &= \text{height of the cylinder} \\ &= h \text{ units} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \text{Volume of the Cuboid} &= \text{length} \times \text{breadth} \times \text{height} \\ &= (\pi r \times r \times h) \text{ cube units} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \text{Volume of the Cylinder} = \pi r^2 h \text{ cube units}$$

Results (Learning Outcomes):

Volume of a Right Circular Cylinder = $\pi r^2 h$ cube units
where r = radius and h = height of the cylinder.

Project 1

Topic: Birthday Party.

Objective:

- (i) To arouse the interest of students in Mathematics.
- (ii) To make a number of articles for birthday party by using combination of two or more of basic shapes of geometry

Materials Required:

Clay/Plasticine, Coloured Chart Paper, Geometry Box, Colour-Box, Fevicol, A Pair of Scissors, Sketch Pens, Rubber Thread, A Cardboard and Decoration Material.

Procedure:

(A) Toys:

Step 1: Using clay or plasticine make a cone and a hemisphere of same base radius.

Step 2: Place and fix their flat faces together

Step 3: Colour and decorate it with a combination of your favorite colours.

Note: You can make a number of toys with a combination of two or more basic shapes of geometry.

(B) Birthday Caps:

Step 1: Cut circles of radius 7 cm (approximately) centered at O from different coloured chart papers.

Step 2: Cut a sector OAB as shown in figure.

Step 3: Fold the remaining papers one by one by bringing the two radii OA and OB together and fix it.

Step 4: Take a rubber thread and tie it along the circular region of each of the cones.

Step 5: Decorate them with sketch colours.

(C) Gift (Pen Stand):

Step 1: Take a rectangular cardboard of size 10 cm \times 20 cm.

Step 2: Fold it to make a cylinder of height 10 cm.

Step 3: Cut a circle of radius 3.5 cm from a cardboard and fix it at one end of the cylinder.

Step 4: Paint and decorate it with colours.

Note: You can make many gifts by using mathematical shapes

(D) Decoration Material (Strips)

Step 1: Cut long rectangular strips of breadth 3 cm from different coloured glazed papers.

Step 2: Make small triangles at the both sides of the strips as shown in figure.
Cut along these triangles.

Step 3: Cut along these triangles

Note: You can use the cuttings of sector BOA left after making birthday caps as decoration material.

Outcomes:

Toys to play (nice round- bottomed toy), Birthday Caps, Gift (Pen Stand), Decoration Material (Strips and Triangles).

Project -2

Topic: Geometry in Real Life

Objective:

To use geometrical concepts effectively in a given situation.

Procedure:

(A) Height of Tower

Step 1: Locate a pole in the school ground.

Step 2: Fix a stick of known height say d_1 units in vertical position in the shadow of pole such that the end point of the shadow of the stick is at the same point as the end of the shadow of the pole.

Step 3: Measure AC (say d units) and DC (say d_2 units)

Step 4: Observe $\triangle ABC$ and $\triangle CDE$ are similar.

Step 5: Using properties of similar triangles

$$\frac{AB}{ED} = \frac{AC}{CD},$$

we get $AB = \frac{dd_1}{d_2}$

Outcome: *Height of the Tower.*

Mathematics Laboratory is a place where students can learn and explore mathematical concepts and verify mathematical facts and theorems through a variety of activities using different types of materials. The activities may be performed by the teacher or the students for exploration, learning and to stimulate interest and develop positive attitude towards mathematics. Finally, I want to emphasize that mathematics laboratory will fulfill the aim of teaching mathematics only if it does not become another period; another burden on students but it becomes the source of joyful learning of mathematics. The teachers should relate mathematics to our daily life in regular classrooms also.

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